

Continuous q-Space Signal Synthesis from Arbitrary Sparse Multi-Shell Measurements

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Abstract. Dense multi-shell diffusion MRI acquisitions provide rich q-space information but require long scan times, limiting their practicality in clinical and large-scale settings. We propose a spatially aware teacher-student framework for reconstructing continuous q-space information from sparse multi-shell observations. The method treats the observed diffusion measurements as an unordered masked set and predicts SHORE coefficients for the center voxel from a lightweight $3 \times 3 \times 3$ neighborhood. Architecturally, the model combines shared per-measurement encoding, gated local-and-wide spatial attention, cross-gradient self-attention, and permutation-invariant pooling, yielding a structured latent representation that can be decoded analytically to synthesize signals at arbitrary q-space locations. To improve robustness under sparse acquisition, we train a teacher on full observations and distill its pooled latent representation into sparse-input student model using an MSE-based feature matching loss. We further employ shell-wise antipodal repulsive sampling and SHORE-consistent rotation augmentation to simulate realistic sparse protocols while preserving physical consistency between inputs and supervision. Experiments on held-out Human Connectome Project subjects show that the proposed method consistently outperforms analytical baselines and recent learning-based reconstruction methods across sparse single-shell and multi-shell settings, with the largest gains in the low-measurement regime. These results demonstrate that combining set-based q-space modeling, local spatial context, and teacher-guided distillation enables accurate and flexible diffusion signal reconstruction from limited observations. Our implementation is available on [GitHub](#).

Keywords: Diffusion MRI reconstruction · q-space signal synthesis · sparse multi-shell acquisition

1 Introduction

Diffusion MRI (dMRI) provides in vivo access to tissue microstructure by measuring signal attenuation under diffusion-sensitizing gradients applied over multiple directions and b-values. Dense multi-shell acquisitions substantially improve

the estimation of white matter organization, microstructural properties, and fiber orientation, but they remain expensive in practice because they require many diffusion-weighted measurements and therefore long scan times [8,3,5,12]. This trade-off between signal richness and acquisition cost remains a major obstacle for routine clinical use, motion-sensitive populations, and large-scale studies, motivating methods that recover dense q-space information from sparse observations.

Early learning-based approaches demonstrated that deep networks can infer missing shells, synthesize high-b signals, or recover signal-derived quantities from reduced acquisitions [8,7,11,3]. However, many of these methods are tied to a fixed acquisition protocol: they assume a predefined number and ordering of diffusion measurements at input, or they require separate models for specific source-target shell mappings [15,11,3]. This limitation is increasingly problematic because modern dMRI studies differ substantially in the number of shells, gradient directions, and b-values. Recent work has made this issue explicit. In particular, DISCUS showed that many previous learning-based methods are acquisition-specific and argued for input-continuous and output-continuous reconstruction that can accept arbitrary diffusion encodings and predict signals at arbitrary q-space locations [5].

A complementary line of work models the diffusion signal continuously using analytical or implicit representations. Classical methods such as spherical harmonics, Simple Harmonic Oscillator Based Reconstruction and Estimation (SHORE), and Mean Apparent Propagator (MAP)-MRI provide interpretable basis expansions that can be queried continuously in angle or q-space [2,18,19,17]. More recently, implicit neural representations have been introduced to exploit spatial coherence in diffusion MRI. NeSH models the diffusion signal continuously in both the angular and spatial domains, while HashEnc represents a spatially continuous field of ODFs on high-resolution dMRI scans [9,4]. Related recent work has also explored continuous dMRI reconstruction with anatomical structure-assisted implicit neural representations, further emphasizing the value of spatially informed continuous modeling [22]. These methods highlight two important observations: first, inter-voxel coherence is valuable for reconstruction; second, continuous representations are attractive for synthesis at unseen locations. At the same time, such approaches are typically optimized at the level of a single subject or scan, which makes cross-subject generalization and deployment under heterogeneous sparse acquisition settings less direct [9,4]. More broadly, recent volumetric INR work has emphasized that fitting an implicit model from scratch for every new volume is computationally inefficient and benefits from transferable priors [23].

These developments reveal a clear gap in the literature. Protocol-specific deep models do not naturally handle arbitrary sparse observation sets, while continuous INR-based methods exploit spatial structure but are commonly fit per subject. What is still missing is a population-trained model that combines the strengths of both directions: a method that treats sparse multi-shell measurements as an unordered set, exploits local spatial context, and predicts a

structured latent representation from which continuous q-space signals can be synthesized analytically.

In this work, we address this gap with a spatially aware teacher-student framework for sparse multi-shell q-space reconstruction. The proposed model takes a lightweight $3 \times 3 \times 3$ neighborhood as input and predicts SHORE coefficients for the center voxel. The teacher is trained with the full acquisition, whereas the student operates on sparse shell-wise subsets and is guided by latent feature distillation. Architecturally, the model combines shared per-measurement encoding, gated local-and-wide spatial attention, cross-gradient self-attention, and permutation-invariant aggregation over the observed measurements. By predicting SHORE coefficients rather than directly regressing signals at fixed queries, the method retains a structured and interpretable latent space while supporting analytic synthesis at arbitrary directions and b-values through the SHORE basis. By conditioning on a local patch rather than absolute coordinates, it exploits inter-voxel coherence without requiring subject-specific coordinate fitting.

Our main contributions are fivefold. ❶ We propose a sparse multi-shell diffusion reconstruction framework that represents observed q-space measurements as an unordered masked set rather than a fixed protocol-specific vector. ❷ We introduce a spatial-first architecture that injects local neighborhood information through gated spatial attention and models cross-gradient dependencies before permutation-invariant aggregation. ❸ We cast sparse q-space reconstruction in a teacher-student setting, where a teacher trained on full acquisitions distills its pooled latent representation into sparse-input students. ❹ We employ SHORE coefficients as a structured latent representation, enabling interpretable and continuous signal synthesis through an analytic decoder. ❺ We demonstrate that the proposed method achieves superior reconstruction performance over state-of-the-art approaches under sparse sampling regimes, with the largest gains in the low-measurement setting where accurate reconstruction is most challenging and most relevant for scan-time reduction.

2 Method

2.1 Problem Formulation and Overview

Our goal is to reconstruct a continuous q-space representation of the diffusion signal at a center voxel from a limited set of observed measurements. Rather than learning this mapping from sparse observations alone, we adopt a teacher-student formulation motivated by missing-modality and incomplete-observation learning [1,13], where a model with access to complete observations guides another model that must operate under partial input. In our setting, the full multi-shell acquisition is available during training, whereas at inference time only a subset of gradients may be observed. We therefore treat the fully observed acquisition as privileged training-time information and use it to train a strong teacher, which then supervises a sparse-input student.

Formally, let $\mathcal{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3 \times 3 \times G \times D}$ denote a local neighborhood centered at voxel v_c , where G is the number of diffusion measurements and $D = 5$ is the

dimensionality of the per-measurement descriptor. For voxel u and measurement g , the input feature is

$$\mathbf{x}_{u,g} = (\sqrt{\tilde{b}_g} g_{x,g}, \sqrt{\tilde{b}_g} g_{y,g}, \sqrt{\tilde{b}_g} g_{z,g}, s_{u,g}, \tilde{b}_g) \in \mathbb{R}^5,$$

where $(g_{x,g}, g_{y,g}, g_{z,g})$ is the diffusion gradient direction, \tilde{b}_g is the normalized shell value, and $s_{u,g}$ is the normalized diffusion signal. The prediction target is the SHORE coefficient vector $\mathbf{c} \in \mathbb{R}^C$ of the center voxel. A binary mask $\mathbf{m} \in \{0, 1\}^G$ indicates which measurements are observed. The teacher operates with full observations, whereas the student receives sparse observations produced by shell-wise directional subsampling.

The model is organized in a *spatial-first* manner. Each observed q-space measurement is first encoded independently, then spatial context is injected into the center voxel before any pooling across gradients is performed, and only afterwards are cross-gradient interactions modeled and aggregated into a fixed-length latent representation. This ordering is important because spatial context should refine each measurement-specific latent before the set of observed gradients is collapsed into a permutation-invariant descriptor.

2.2 Teacher Network

The teacher receives the full observation set and predicts SHORE coefficients for the center voxel through four stages: per-measurement encoding, spatial contextualization, cross-gradient interaction, and invariant aggregation followed by coefficient prediction.

Per-measurement encoder. Let $u \in \{1, \dots, 27\}$ index a voxel location within the flattened $3 \times 3 \times 3$ neighborhood and let g index an observed diffusion measurement. For each voxel-measurement pair (u, g) , we encode the descriptor $\mathbf{x}_{u,g} \in \mathbb{R}^D$ with a shared multi-layer perceptron ϕ , yielding $\mathbf{h}_{u,g} = \phi(\mathbf{x}_{u,g}) \in \mathbb{R}^H$, where H denotes the latent dimensionality. The encoder is applied independently to every valid (u, g) pair and shares weights across all spatial locations and gradients.

This design is inspired by set-based modeling [24,16]. The observed q-space samples form an unordered set, and therefore the first stage of the network should be permutation-equivariant with respect to gradient order. A shared MLP provides a simple and effective way to encode each measurement before introducing structured spatial and q-space interactions. Missing measurements are handled by masking invalid entries during encoding, attention, and pooling.

Spatial-first contextualization. After encoding, the latent tensor over the local patch is denoted by $\mathbf{H} \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3 \times 3 \times G \times H}$. We extract the latent sequence $\mathbf{h}_{c,g}$ of the center voxel and enrich it with information from its surrounding neighborhood. Importantly, this spatial contextualization is performed separately for each gradient index g . This reflects the fact that a measurement identified by

its q-space coordinates should first be interpreted in its local anatomical context before being mixed with other measurements in q-space.

To do so, we flatten the spatial neighborhood into $N = 27$ locations and construct two attention branches. The first is a *local* branch restricted to the six face-neighbors of the center voxel, and the second is a *wide* branch defined on all non-center neighbors. For each branch, the center feature acts as a query, the neighboring features act as keys and values, and attention scores are modulated by explicit relative position features. If $\mathbf{q}_g = W_q \mathbf{h}_{c,g}$, $\mathbf{k}_{n,g} = W_k \mathbf{h}_{n,g}$, and $\mathbf{v}_{n,g} = W_v \mathbf{h}_{n,g}$, then the attention score for neighbor n is

$$a_{n,g} = w^\top \tanh(\mathbf{q}_g + \mathbf{k}_{n,g} + \psi(\mathbf{p}_n)),$$

where \mathbf{p}_n encodes the relative position of neighbor n with respect to the center voxel. In our implementation, \mathbf{p}_n contains signed offsets, normalized offsets, absolute offsets, Manhattan distance, and squared Euclidean distance. The branch-specific attention weights are then $\alpha_{n,g} = \text{softmax}(a_{n,g})$, computed over valid neighbors only, and the corresponding branch context is $\mathbf{c}_g^{\text{branch}} = \sum_n \alpha_{n,g} \mathbf{v}_{n,g}$.

We use two spatial branches because local and broader neighborhood information play different roles in diffusion MRI. The face-neighbors emphasize immediate tissue continuity and sharp local structure, whereas the wider branch provides contextual support in regions with complex fiber geometry or local heterogeneity. Instead of forcing one fixed neighborhood model to explain both effects, we let the network learn them separately and fuse them adaptively. Specifically, the branch outputs are concatenated, mixed through a small MLP, and gated with the center feature:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{c}}_g = \psi_{\text{mix}}([\mathbf{c}_g^{\text{loc}}; \mathbf{c}_g^{\text{wide}}]), \quad \mathbf{r}_g = \sigma(W_r[\mathbf{h}_{c,g}; \tilde{\mathbf{c}}_g]), \quad \mathbf{c}_g = \mathbf{r}_g \odot \tilde{\mathbf{c}}_g.$$

The final spatially contextualized feature is obtained by a residual update,

$$\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_g = \mathbf{h}_{c,g} + \gamma \odot \mathbf{c}_g,$$

where γ is a learnable residual scaling vector. This residual formulation keeps the center voxel as the primary signal carrier while introducing neighborhood information as a controlled correction.

Cross-gradient interaction and invariant aggregation. Once spatial context has been injected into each gradient-specific feature, we model dependencies across the observed gradients themselves. This step is necessary because diffusion measurements are not independent: measurements from different directions and shells jointly encode the underlying q-space structure, and their relationships become especially important under sparse sampling. To capture these dependencies, we apply multi-head self-attention to the sequence $\{\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_g\}_{g=1}^G$, yielding a residual q-space correction $\Delta \mathbf{h}_g$. This produces a second latent stream that explicitly models interactions among observed gradients after spatial context has already been incorporated.

We then aggregate both streams in a permutation-invariant way. The first stream is pooled from the contextualized features $\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_g$, resulting in \mathbf{z}_{base} , and

the second is pooled from the q-space attention correction $\Delta\mathbf{h}_g$, resulting in \mathbf{z}_{attn} . For both streams, we use mean-max pooling, that is, we concatenate the masked mean and masked maximum across the gradient dimension. Mean pooling summarizes the global trend of the observed q-space samples, while max pooling preserves salient directional evidence that may otherwise be diluted by averaging. The final latent descriptor is

$$\mathbf{z} = \mathbf{z}_{\text{base}} + \beta \odot \mathbf{z}_{\text{attn}},$$

where β is a learnable scale. The predicted SHORE coefficients are then obtained with a final predictor MLP,

$$\hat{\mathbf{c}} = \rho(\mathbf{z}).$$

This final stage preserves permutation invariance with respect to gradient order while postponing invariant aggregation until after both spatial and cross-gradient reasoning have taken place, allowing the network to build a richer representation before compressing it into a fixed-length descriptor.

2.3 Student Network and Latent Distillation

The student uses the same backbone architecture as the teacher but operates under sparse input conditions. More precisely, the student receives the same $3 \times 3 \times 3$ patch, but only a subset of q-space measurements is marked as observed by the binary mask. Using the same architecture for teacher and student isolates the effect of privileged full-observation training from changes in model capacity and makes the comparison between dense and sparse regimes conceptually clean.

The student is supervised not only by the reconstruction objective but also by feature-level knowledge distillation from the teacher. Let \mathbf{z}_T and \mathbf{z}_S denote the final pooled latent representations of teacher and student, respectively. We distill this feature rather than earlier per-measurement features or the final SHORE coefficients. Distilling the final output would add limited information because the coefficients are already constrained by the supervised reconstruction loss, whereas earlier per-measurement features are overly sensitive to the exact observation mask and therefore do not provide a stable comparison space between teacher and student. The feature \mathbf{z} offers a better compromise: it is computed after spatial reasoning and cross-gradient interaction, yet it is already permutation-invariant and robust to the varying number of observed gradients. In this sense, \mathbf{z} acts as a compact representation of the teacher’s understanding of the local q-space structure, and distillation encourages the student to recover this representation from sparse inputs.

2.4 Training Objective

Let \mathbf{c} and $\hat{\mathbf{c}}$ denote the ground-truth and predicted SHORE coefficient vectors, respectively, and let \mathbf{s} and $\hat{\mathbf{s}} = \Phi\hat{\mathbf{c}}$ denote the measured and reconstructed diffusion signals. We supervise both coefficient accuracy and signal reconstruction through

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{obj}} = \lambda_c \|\hat{\mathbf{c}} - \mathbf{c}\|_2^2 + \lambda_s \|\hat{\mathbf{s}} - \mathbf{s}\|_2^2,$$

where λ_c and λ_s weight coefficient- and signal-domain supervision.

For the student, we additionally distill the pooled latent representation of the teacher. The distillation term is

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{KD}} = \|\mathbf{z}_S - \mathbf{z}_T\|_2^2.$$

The teacher is trained using only \mathcal{L}_{obj} , while the student is trained with

$$\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{L}_{\text{obj}} + \lambda_{\text{KD}}\mathcal{L}_{\text{KD}},$$

where λ_{KD} controls the strength of distillation.

2.5 Rotation Augmentation and SHORE-Consistent Supervision

To improve robustness to orientation variability, we apply random rotation augmentation during training. This step is particularly important to prevent the network from overfitting to the specific training b -vector configuration. In our setting, the shell values remain fixed and only the gradient directions are rotated, so the augmentation encourages the model to learn a more general mapping from sparse q-space observations to the underlying diffusion signal rather than memorizing a particular directional sampling pattern.

For each augmented sample, all diffusion gradient directions are jointly rotated by a random 3D rotation matrix $R \in SO(3)$, sampled uniformly from quaternion space. If \mathbf{g}_m denotes the original gradient direction of measurement m , the rotated direction is $\mathbf{g}'_m = R\mathbf{g}_m$.

This augmentation directly affects the network input, since each measurement is represented by its q-space coordinates $(\sqrt{\tilde{b}}g_x, \sqrt{\tilde{b}}g_y, \sqrt{\tilde{b}}g_z, s, \tilde{b})$. After rotation, the input becomes $(\sqrt{\tilde{b}}g'_x, \sqrt{\tilde{b}}g'_y, \sqrt{\tilde{b}}g'_z, s, \tilde{b})$. Thus, the shell value \tilde{b} and signal value s remain unchanged, while only the directional components are rotated.

A crucial point is that the SHORE supervision must be transformed consistently with the rotated acquisition geometry. Since SHORE coefficients are basis-dependent, rotating the gradient directions changes the corresponding SHORE design matrix. Therefore, for each augmented sample, we recompute the SHORE basis matrix $\Phi' = \Phi(\mathbf{q}')$ from the rotated b -vectors while keeping the original b -values fixed.

To obtain valid supervision after rotation, we do not reuse the original SHORE coefficient vector directly. Instead, we preserve the signal represented by the original SHORE model and re-express that same signal in the rotated SHORE basis. Let Φ and \mathbf{c} denote the original SHORE design matrix and coefficient vector, respectively. The corresponding signal is first reconstructed as $\mathbf{s} = \Phi\mathbf{c}$. We then compute rotated coefficients \mathbf{c}' by solving

$$\mathbf{c}' = \arg \min_{\mathbf{c}} \|\Phi'\mathbf{c} - \mathbf{s}\|_2^2.$$

In practice, this least-squares problem is solved using the pseudoinverse, that is $\mathbf{c}' = \Phi'^+\mathbf{s}$.

Finally, the rotated coefficients are normalized using the training-set SHORE statistics and used as the supervision target for the augmented sample. This procedure ensures label-consistent augmentation: both the rotated q-space inputs and the SHORE targets correspond to the same acquisition geometry. As a result, the model is encouraged to learn rotationally robust q-space structure rather than overfitting to a particular set of training b -vectors.

3 Experimental Setup

3.1 Dataset and Preprocessing

We evaluate the proposed method on the HCP100 subset of the Human Connectome Project (HCP) [21], which provides high-quality multi-shell diffusion MRI with three nonzero shells at approximately $b \in \{1000, 2000, 3000\} \text{ s/mm}^2$, each containing 90 diffusion-weighted measurements, together with 18 b_0 volumes. The acquisition protocol is characterized by a gradient separation of $\Delta \approx 43.1 \text{ ms}$ and gradient duration $\delta \approx 10.6 \text{ ms}$. Such dense multi-shell acquisitions provide rich microstructural information but remain costly in practice due to prolonged scan times.

We use the minimally preprocessed HCP data and restrict the analysis to white matter voxels using white matter masks obtained with FSL [10]. For each voxel, diffusion-weighted measurements are normalized by the mean b_0 signal, yielding unitless normalized signals and reducing global intensity variation. As supervision targets, we fit voxel-wise SHORE coefficients from the full reference acquisition using the DIPY [6] implementation of SHORE with a fixed radial order of 6. These coefficient vectors are treated as ground truth. We additionally precompute the SHORE basis rows $\Phi(\mathbf{q})$ for all gradient directions and b -values used during training and evaluation, enabling efficient reconstruction at arbitrary q-space query points.

Subjects are split at the subject level into 80 training, 10 validation, and 10 test subjects.

3.2 Sparse Subset Construction

To simulate reduced-acquisition settings, we generate sparse directional subsets independently for each subject and each shell using the subject-specific b -vectors. Candidate directions are grouped into antipodally symmetric pairs, and subsets are then constructed using an antipodal repulsive sampling strategy to promote approximately uniform spherical coverage. Concretely, a direction is selected at random, the corresponding antipodal pair is retained, and additional pairs are then chosen greedily to maximize angular separation. We consider subsets of 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 40, and 50 directions per shell.

These subsets are used to define the sparse observation masks for student training and evaluation. In the multi-shell setting, subsampling is applied independently within each shell.

3.3 Baselines

We compare the proposed method against both analytical and learning-based baselines. As analytical baselines, we use the DIPY implementations of SHORE and MAP-MRI [6]. SHORE is evaluated with radial order 6, matching the target representation used in our framework, while MAP-MRI is evaluated with radial order 8. As a learning-based continuous reconstruction baseline, we compare against DISCUS [5]. These baselines cover protocol-flexible analytical reconstruction as well as recent neural continuous q-space modeling.

3.4 Implementation and Training Details

All models are implemented in PyTorch [20] 2.5.0 and trained on randomly sampled white matter voxels. At each iteration, we sample a subject and a spatial location inside the white matter mask. The network input is a $3 \times 3 \times 3$ neighborhood centered at the selected voxel, while the prediction target is the SHORE coefficient vector of the center voxel.

We first train a teacher model using the full multi-shell acquisition. Optimization is performed with Adam [14] using an initial learning rate of 10^{-3} and a polynomial decay schedule with power 0.9. To improve orientation diversity, we apply random rotation augmentation with probability 0.2 by rotating the gradient directions while preserving the physical consistency of the diffusion signal and the corresponding SHORE supervision.

The student model is trained under sparse-acquisition settings. For each shell, the input is restricted to direction subsets obtained by antipodal repulsive sampling, thereby simulating reduced angular coverage while preserving approximately uniform spherical sampling. We use $\lambda_c = \lambda_s = 1$ for the reconstruction objective and $\lambda_{KD} = 0.8$ for latent distillation.

Training is performed with a batch size of 512 for 125,000 iterations, where 2,500 iterations correspond to one epoch. All experiments are run on a single NVIDIA H100 GPU with 92 GB VRAM, and the total training time is approximately 15 hours.

3.5 Evaluation Metrics

We evaluate reconstruction quality in the diffusion signal domain. Metrics are computed per voxel using the full reference diffusion-weighted signal vector and are then averaged over the white matter mask and all test subjects.

Let $\mathbf{s}, \hat{\mathbf{s}} \in \mathbb{R}^G$ denote the ground-truth and reconstructed diffusion signals. We report normalized mean squared error, defined as $\text{NMSE} = \|\hat{\mathbf{s}} - \mathbf{s}\|_2^2 / \|\mathbf{s}\|_2^2$, and peak signal-to-noise ratio, defined as $\text{PSNR} = 10 \log_{10}(S_{\max}^2 / \text{MSE})$, where $\text{MSE} = \frac{1}{G} \sum_{g=1}^G (\hat{s}_g - s_g)^2$. Since the diffusion signals are normalized by the mean $b0$ signal, we use $S_{\max} = 1$. When reported in tables, NMSE is expressed as a percentage. All metrics are evaluated across multiple undersampling regimes to assess robustness under increasingly sparse acquisition settings.

Table 1: Quantitative comparison of the proposed method and baseline approaches under sparse sampling in the $b = 1000$ shell. Each row corresponds to a different number of retained gradients, and performance is evaluated on the HCP test set by reconstructing the full diffusion signal. PSNR (dB) and NMSE (%) are reported, with **blue** and **red** indicating the best and second-best results, respectively, for each metric and sampling budget.

# gradients	DISCUS [5]		SHORE [18]		MAP [19]		Ours	
	PSNR \uparrow	NMSE \downarrow						
5	20.61	6.02	17.87	11.63	18.35	10.06	21.81	4.51
10	21.29	4.99	18.44	9.96	19.15	8.24	23.01	3.36
15	21.50	4.75	18.57	9.65	19.46	7.62	23.44	3.03
20	21.66	4.58	18.66	9.45	19.57	7.41	23.66	2.88
25	21.77	4.48	18.69	9.36	19.67	7.22	23.81	2.77
30	21.89	4.36	18.70	9.33	19.75	7.09	23.92	2.70
40	22.01	4.23	18.76	9.22	19.83	6.95	24.06	2.62
50	22.11	4.13	18.82	9.08	19.86	6.89	24.15	2.57

4 Results

Fig. 1 summarizes the PSNR obtained by the proposed method and competing approaches across different shell combinations and sampling budgets. Table 1 reports the detailed quantitative results for the $b = 1000$ shell in terms of PSNR and NMSE.

Overall, the proposed method achieves the best reconstruction performance in the sparse regime across nearly all evaluated settings. The advantage is most pronounced at low and moderate numbers of retained gradients, where the reconstruction problem is most difficult and where scan-time reduction is most relevant in practice. This trend indicates that the proposed combination of spatial context modeling and teacher-guided latent distillation provides a stronger inductive bias than analytical fitting or prior learning-based baselines when only limited q-space information is available.

Single-shell reconstruction. For the $b = 1000$ shell, the proposed method consistently outperforms all baselines for every sampling budget shown in Table 1. At 5 retained gradients, our method achieves 21.81 dB PSNR, compared with 20.61 dB for DISCUS, 18.35 dB for MAP, and 17.87 dB for SHORE. The corresponding NMSE is reduced to 4.51%, compared with 6.02% for DISCUS, 10.06% for MAP, and 11.63% for SHORE. Relative to the strongest competing baseline, DISCUS, this corresponds to a 25.1% reduction in NMSE. As the sampling budget increases, the proposed method remains consistently superior. At 50 retained gradients, it reaches 24.15 dB PSNR with 2.57% NMSE, whereas DISCUS achieves 22.11 dB and 4.13% NMSE, corresponding to a 37.8% NMSE reduction. Overall, across all sampling budgets in the $b = 1000$ shell, the proposed method

Fig. 1: PSNR comparison between the proposed method and competing approaches across shell combinations and sampling budgets. Each subplot shows the reconstruction PSNR (dB) versus the number of diffusion gradients retained per shell using antipodal repulsive sampling. The panels cover both single-shell ($b = 2000$, $b = 3000$) and multi-shell settings ($1000 + 2000$, $1000 + 3000$, $2000 + 3000$, and $1000 + 2000 + 3000$). In the multi-shell case, an x-axis value of k denotes that k gradients are selected from each shell, resulting in a total of $k \times S$ retained gradients for a configuration with S shells. Higher PSNR indicates better reconstruction quality.

improves PSNR over DISCUS by 1.20–2.04 dB while substantially reducing reconstruction error.

A similar trend is observed in Fig. 1 for the other single-shell settings. In particular, the performance margin is also substantial for the $b = 3000$ shell, where the proposed method remains clearly above DISCUS, MAP, and SHORE across all budgets. This suggests that the learned spatial and q-space priors are especially beneficial when the reconstruction task becomes more challenging, as is typically the case at higher diffusion weighting.

Multi-shell reconstruction. In the multi-shell setting, the proposed method again performs best in the low-budget regime and remains highly competitive as the number of retained gradients increases. For the $1000 + 2000$, $1000 + 3000$, $2000 + 3000$, and $1000 + 2000 + 3000$ settings, our method achieves the highest PSNR at small and intermediate sampling budgets, demonstrating strong sample efficiency. In other words, given the same number of gradients retained per shell, the proposed model is able to recover the full diffusion signal more accurately than the competing approaches when measurements are scarce.

As the number of retained gradients increases further, the gap to SHORE becomes smaller in some multi-shell settings, and SHORE eventually matches

or slightly exceeds the proposed method at the highest budgets for some shell combinations. This behavior is expected in our setup and should be interpreted carefully. The supervision targets used for training are SHORE coefficients fitted to the full reference acquisition, which introduces a favorable model alignment for the SHORE baseline as the input approaches dense sampling. Under such conditions, analytical SHORE fitting increasingly operates close to the target signal family used for supervision, leading to a natural saturation effect near full angular coverage.

Importantly, this does not reduce the practical relevance of the proposed method. The primary goal is not to replace dense multi-shell fitting when nearly all measurements are already available, but rather to achieve accurate reconstruction under limited acquisition. It is precisely in this sparse regime, which is the clinically meaningful operating point for scan-time reduction, that the proposed method provides the clearest and most consistent advantage. The results therefore indicate that the method is particularly well suited to low-measurement protocols, where direct analytical fitting is underdetermined and where learned spatial and q-space priors are most valuable.

Overall interpretation. Taken together, the results highlight three main observations. First, the proposed model is markedly more effective than competing approaches in the low-gradient regime, showing that spatial context aggregation and latent distillation are especially useful when q-space evidence is limited. Second, the gains are consistent across both single-shell and multi-shell settings, indicating that the method generalizes well across different sparse acquisition scenarios. Third, the narrowing gap to SHORE at high multi-shell budgets is explained by the SHORE-derived supervision itself and therefore reflects target-model alignment rather than a weakness of the proposed sparse-reconstruction strategy. From an application perspective, the most relevant operating point remains the sparse regime, and in this regime the proposed method delivers the strongest overall reconstruction quality.

5 Ablation Studies

We performed ablation experiments to quantify the contribution of the main components of the proposed framework. Table 2 summarizes the results. Teacher ablations were evaluated under full-observation reconstruction, where all diffusion measurements were available as input. This setting serves as an upper-bound reference and isolates the effect of the architectural design itself. Student ablations were evaluated in the sparse setting with 5 retained gradients from the $b = 1000$ shell, which reflects the most challenging low-measurement regime.

We first analyzed the effect of progressively enriching the teacher architecture with spatial context. Starting from the invariant voxel MLP baseline, adding a simple CNN-based spatial context module reduced NMSE from 2.35% to 2.25%, corresponding to a relative error reduction of 4.3%. Replacing this fixed neighborhood aggregation with the proposed gated spatial attention further reduced

Table 2: Ablation study of the proposed framework. NMSE is reported in %. The teacher is evaluated under full-observation reconstruction, while the student is evaluated in the sparse setting with 5 retained gradients from the $b = 1000$ shell. For each block, Δ denotes the improvement in NMSE relative to the corresponding baseline setting. Lower is better.

Setting	Variant	NMSE (%) \downarrow	Δ
Teacher architecture	Invariant voxel MLP	2.35	–
	+ CNN spatial context	2.25	-0.10
	+ Gated spatial attention (ours)	2.18	-0.17
Teacher augmentation	Without rotation augmentation	2.21	–
	With rotation augmentation	2.18	-0.03
Student distillation	Without distillation	4.69	–
	With Distillation	4.51	-0.18

NMSE to 2.18%, yielding a 7.2% relative improvement over the invariant baseline and a further 3.1% reduction compared with the CNN context model. These results indicate that spatial context is beneficial even in the full-observation setting and that adaptive neighborhood aggregation is more effective than a fixed convolutional context encoder.

We next evaluated the impact of the proposed physically consistent rotation augmentation in the teacher. Introducing rotation augmentation reduced NMSE from 2.21% to 2.18%, corresponding to a relative improvement of 1.4%. Although the gain is smaller than that obtained from the architectural changes, it is consistent and confirms that orientation-aware augmentation improves robustness without changing the acquisition shell structure. This is particularly important in our setting, where the input representation depends explicitly on the gradient directions and could otherwise overfit to a specific training b-vector configuration.

Finally, we evaluated the role of latent distillation for the sparse-input student. When trained without distillation, the student achieved an NMSE of 4.69%. Distilling the pooled latent representation from the teacher using an MSE loss reduced the error to 4.51%, corresponding to a relative improvement of 3.8%. This result shows that the teacher transfers useful structural information beyond the direct reconstruction objective and that latent supervision is particularly beneficial in the extreme sparse regime, where the student has limited q-space evidence available at input.

Together, these ablations show that the gains of the proposed framework do not arise from a single design choice, but from the complementary interaction of spatial context modeling, physically consistent augmentation, and teacher-guided latent supervision.

6 Limitations

The present study has several limitations that also point to natural directions for future work. First, the proposed model is supervised using SHORE coefficients fitted from the full acquisition. As a result, the target representation inherits the assumptions of SHORE, and this induces a favorable alignment for analytical SHORE fitting at high sampling budgets. This behavior is reflected in the multi-shell experiments, where SHORE becomes increasingly competitive and can surpass the proposed method when the number of observed gradients approaches dense sampling. In this sense, the current framework should be interpreted primarily as a method for robust sparse reconstruction rather than as a replacement for dense analytical fitting near full acquisition.

Second, we used a SHORE radial order of 6 throughout the study, which provides a practical compromise between representational power and fitting stability. While this choice yields a compact and well-behaved latent target space, higher SHORE orders may further increase representational fidelity and could potentially improve reconstruction quality, especially in richer sampling regimes. Exploring this trade-off is an important direction for future work.

Third, spatial context is restricted to a local $3 \times 3 \times 3$ neighborhood. This was chosen deliberately to keep the model lightweight and to focus on immediate anatomical support, but it does not capture longer-range white matter organization that may be informative in complex fiber regions. Extending the framework to larger or multi-scale spatial context could therefore provide additional gains.

7 Conclusion

We presented a spatially aware teacher-student framework for sparse multi-shell diffusion MRI reconstruction. The proposed method treats observed q-space measurements as an unordered masked set and predicts SHORE coefficients for the center voxel from a $3 \times 3 \times 3$ neighborhood using shared per-measurement encoding, gated spatial attention, cross-gradient self-attention, and permutation-invariant pooling. A teacher trained on full observations transfers its pooled latent representation to sparse-input students via MSE-based distillation, enabling robust reconstruction from limited measurements. Combined with SHORE-consistent supervision, shell-wise antipodal repulsive sampling, and physically consistent rotation augmentation, the framework provides an accurate and interpretable approach for continuous q-space synthesis. On held-out HCP subjects, it consistently outperformed analytical and learning-based baselines across sparse single-shell and multi-shell settings, with the largest gains in the low-measurement regime most relevant for scan-time reduction.

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